

A discrete lesion-bearing leaf is fixed with double-sided adhesive tape on the acrylic rain protector without detaching the leaf from the plant. A basin-shaped acrylic capsule 40 mm long is placed just beneath the lesion. Collection is at 1- or 24-h intervals. Spores can be counted immediately or the capsule can be sealed with masking tape and the spores counted a few weeks or months later. When spores are counted 0.1 ml of 0.02% Tween 20 solution are added to the capsule and the conidia counted with a hemacytometer. Spores in one capsule can be counted in less than 10 min.

The table shows the number of conidia released from a single lesion in Jul 1987. The amount varies, depending

P. oryzae conidia released from discrete blast lesions^a of rice cultivars Jinheung and Jinju. Korea, 1987.

Date surveyed	Conidia (no.)									
	Jinheung					Jinju				
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
3 Jul	40	80	500	220	40	160	140	460	80	160
4 Jul	280	460	320	420	60	600	220	980	200	520
5 Jul	140	180	680	80	340	700	300	720	120	140
6 Jul	100	460	320	100	120	720	0	280	300	960
7 Jul	100	380	920	320	540	700	280	740	280	220
8 Jul	120	5,360	10,620	2,620	5,660	15,800	7,060	13,720	8,860	5,420
9 Jul	300	2,720	5,900	940	3,480	12,600	2,680	30,560	4,240	10,720
10 Jul	2,960	—	3,000	880	1,200	—	820	1,240	1,500	—

^aLesions appeared 2 Jul.

upon the condition of the lesion as well as on the weather. The maximum number exceeded 30,000 conidia/d,

suggesting the usefulness of a KY type spore trap to study conidia release under natural conditions. □

Screening antibiotics for their control of bacterial blight (BB)

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No effective control against rice BB has been reported so far. A few antibiotics,

Effect of antibiotics on control of BB of rice. Aduthurai, India, Aug 1987.

Antibiotic ^a	Disease intensity ^b	
	Grade ^c	Leaf area affected (%)
Chloramphenicol	3.6 a	11.0 a
Streptomycin	5.6 b	32.2 b
Oxytetracycline	6.4 bcd	41.8 bcd
Streptocycline	6.3 bcd	40.6 bcd
Streptomycin + penicillin	5.7 bc	33.4 bc
Erythrocin	5.6 b	32.2 b
Ampicillin	5.7 bc	33.4 bc
Cloxacillin	6.4 bcd	41.8 bcd
Amoxycillin	6.6 cd	44.2 cd
Cephalexin	6.9 cde	47.8 cd
Ampicillin + cloxacillin	7.3 de	57.5 de
Amoxycillin + cloxacillin	6.3 bcd	40.6 bcd
Trimethoprim + sulphamethoxazole	6.4 bcd	41.8 bcd
Control	7.4 e	60.0 e

^aCombinations of antibiotics are manufacturer formulations. ^bIn a column, means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at P = 0.05 by DMRT. ^cBy the Standard evaluation system for rice scale.

such as streptomycin and oxytetracycline, have been tried with little success. We evaluated several new combinations of antibiotics and commonly available antibiotics for their efficacy in disease control.

Rice variety ADT38 was grown in the field Aug-Nov 1987. At maximum tillering, plants were sprayed with 1,000 ppm concentrations of different antibiotics, with 3 replications. After

24 h, leaves were clip-inoculated with 72-h-old *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* culture (10⁸ cfu/ml). Disease intensity and leaf area affected were assessed 16 d after inoculation.

Of the antibiotics tested, only chloramphenicol effectively controlled BB (see table). In chloramphenicol treated leaves, only 11% of the leaf area was affected; in unsprayed leaves, 60% of the leaf area was affected. □

Occurrence of bacterial leaf streak (BLS) in Nigeria

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During a survey, symptoms of BLS were noticed on rice variety Gwangulu (ex-China), popularly grown in the irrigated fields of Gafan 2 in Kadawa, Northern Nigeria. Later, BG90-2, also a lowland variety, showed symptoms. In both varieties, symptoms consisted of

narrow, linear, yellowish lesions with the bacterial ooze droplets characteristic of BLS.

The disease was identified as caused by *X. c.* pv. *oryzicola* by appropriate laboratory tests. No authenticated record of this disease in Nigeria had existed.

Similar symptoms were seen on IR46 in Garoua fields of northern Cameroon (SEMRY) during a 1985 survey. In both Nigeria and Cameroon, disease incidence was of low intensity and did not affect the crop. □

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